

Advancing Data and AI Competency for Effective and Trustworthy Decision Making in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA)

Stakeholder Consultation Report

Published by:

Data for Policy CIC

November 2024

This document provides an overview of the second regional strategic dialogue of the **Data for Policy SSA Engagement Programme**, held on **25–26 October 2023, in Accra, Ghana**. Building on insights from the first convening, this session brought together participants from academia, governance, and industry to share perspectives from West Africa.

Cite as: Data for Policy Sub-Saharan Africa Programme: Consultation Reports, November 2024
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237003>

Table of Contents

ADVANCING DATA AND AI COMPETENCY FOR EFFECTIVE AND TRUSTWORTHY DECISION MAKING IN SSA	3
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2. BACKGROUND	4
3. STRUCTURE	5
4. INSIGHTS.....	6
4.1 Navigating Complexity: Data, AI, and Advanced Computation in Decision-Making.....	6
4.2 Fostering a Vibrant GovTech Industry across Africa.....	8
4.4 Impact of West-African Research at the Nexus of Data and Policy	11
4.5 Convergence of Technology and Grassroot Engagement.....	12
5. CONCLUSION.....	13
7. ANNEX.....	17
Strategic Consultation Agenda.....	17
8. PARTNERS' PROFILES	21
Institute of Statistical Social and Economic Research	21
Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation	21
Cambridge University Press	21
Evans School of Policy Analysis & Research Group, Evans School of Public Policy & Governance, University of Washington.....	22

Advancing Data and AI Competency for Effective and Trustworthy Decision Making in SSA

25-26 October 2023 | ISSER Annex, University of Ghana, Legon, Accra

1. Executive Summary

At Data for Policy CIC (DfP) we are dedicated to harnessing the power of data, AI, and emerging technologies to shape a more informed, equitable, and sustainable future for all. Guided by our commitment to inclusivity and collaboration, we cultivate an open culture with responsible innovation and foster dynamic knowledge exchange between academia, public, and private sectors, spanning diverse disciplines and geographies, and empowering policymakers at both global and local levels to effectively address complex challenges with the help of cutting-edge technologies and methods. Our strategy revolves around three principles: bridging research and policy application, fostering global-local synergies, and promoting open innovation aligned with public interest.

Although a global network, our assessments showed that we have limited participation from researchers, policy makers, and practitioners from and working within Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Thus, we began our SSA focused programming with the aim of collaboratively addressing the unique regional challenges and elevating regional insight on data science, AI, and emerging technology roles in policy making on the global stage. Our first convening was held at the Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA), gathering thought leaders from East and South Africa. This was followed by a period of reflection and research, to produce a plan for DfP's strategic development in SSA.

To complement our first convening, we sought to obtain perspectives from West Africa. We now report a second regional strategic dialogue 25-26 October in Accra, Ghana called *Advancing Data and AI Competency for Effective and Trustworthy Decision Making in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA)*. This report presents happenings and findings from this session where participants from academia, governance, and industry identified challenges including the need for decolonisation in knowledge creation, fostering local innovations, enhancing computational competencies, bridging the research-policy gap, and balancing private sector data stewardship with public benefit. The dialogue also highlighted the potential for SSA to contribute innovative research and technological solutions globally, despite systemic constraints like infrastructure and data governance issues. Critical next steps proposed were on co-creating policies and regional regulatory frameworks for interoperability and useful practice, autonomy, capacity building, equity, data stewardship, improving data quality and sharing, and investing in data networks.

There are various national, regional, and global programmes that push for data-driven policy making within SSA, yet Data for Policy CIC is unique in its comprehensive approach in addressing the decolonisation of data science and AI governance, focus on regional autonomy, and fostering multi-disciplinary methods that include policymakers, researchers, civil society, and the private sector.

As an organization rooted in the global south and operating from the global north, we are dedicated to placing SSA research, policy, civil society, and tech leaders at the forefront of directing collaborative and impactful initiatives. We commit to fostering co-creation, leveraging our extensive network and expertise to amplify local voices and expertise. Our approach is grounded in mutual respect and the shared goal of harnessing data and technology for sustainable development, guided by the knowledge and leadership of SSA stakeholders. Thus, participants see DfP as an essential partner in advancing data for policy in SSA.

2. Background

DfP's mission is to enable strategic utilisation of data, artificial intelligence (AI), and associated technologies to shape a more informed, equitable, and sustainable future for all. We do this by cultivating an open culture that encourages responsible innovation and fosters dynamic knowledge exchange between academia, governance, and private sector. Recognising key opportunities, we have developed a comprehensive programme designed to connect researchers, policy makers, and diverse stakeholders. Through both direct initiatives and strategic partnerships, we facilitate interdisciplinary dialogues, support online platforms for knowledge sharing and collaboration, and pioneer knowledge management strategies.

African methodologies and tools that effectively link data to policy are beneficial and hold the potential for global impact. These methods include using demographic and health survey insights for health policy, applying geospatial data into urban planning, shaping policy with community based participatory research, guiding budgeting and allocation with revenue forecasting via predictive AI, and empowering civil society to adequately respond to policy through open data initiatives. Reciprocally, an infusion of global expertise and networks can accelerate the African data and innovation ecosystem.

Therefore, since 2022 and in collaboration with the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and the Evans School of Public Policy & Governance at University of Washington, DfP has proactively engaged with sub-Saharan African stakeholders to build shared understanding, vision, and direction on how to support regional actors in expediting African global engagement and impact at the nexus of data and policy.

Our first stakeholder consultation meeting gave us a number of pointers based on East/South Africa, and following this we developed a preliminary regional strategy proposal. In this, we rearticulate our activities, adding detail and further context. We see these as resting on three axioms:

- Bridging the gap between advanced computational and technological research, ensuring research is not only understood but its insights are effectively applied in policy and practice
- Merging global platforms for collaboration and sharing research, findings, and systems with local knowledge generation, innovation, and impact
- Harmonising private sector's proprietary and frontier dynamics with open, responsible innovation aimed at public benefit

While AI is increasingly dominating global discussions, it is important to understand that its implications are deeply rooted in regional and local specificities. Thus, Sub-Saharan Africa's proactive and sustained engagement on leveraging AI and data science optimally is essential.

Research institutions, professional networks, tech companies, and governments have already begun discussions that underscore the unique and rich data environment of SSA. Expertise from the region, especially in harnessing data science and AI to address urgent challenges like climate change adaptation, food security, and inequalities, is gaining momentum and international attention. This dynamic sets the stage for unprecedented cross-regional learning, connectivity, and growth.

As with our Nairobi meeting, the event in Ghana explored opportunities for enhancing Sub-Saharan Africa's role in the global data-for-policy discourse and fostering data and AI proficiency to ensure informed and reliable decision-making.

3. Structure

In October 2023, DfP and the Institute of Statistical, Social and Economic Research (ISSER) at the University of Ghana co-hosted a pivotal strategic consultation on data science, artificial intelligence, and decision-making within the West African context: *Advancing Data and AI Competency for Effective and Trustworthy Decision Making in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA)*. This programme gathered 30 thought leaders from West African academia, research, policy, and industry working in AI and data for policy fields to gain deeper understanding of and integrate regional happenings and learnings. It focused on themes within data for policy and three complementary focus areas identified by DfP: Navigating Complexity: Data, AI, and Advanced Computation in Decision-Making; Fostering a Vibrant GovTech Industry; and the Convergence of Technology and Grassroot Engagement.

Similar to the previous strategic consultation in Nairobi, the two-day event was designed to foster comprehensive and engaging dialogue and sharing of insights and actionable strategies on integrating regionally sourced data science and AI into governance frameworks.

The event commenced with opening remarks and an address to set the stage on the importance of increased competency and readiness within the public sector. This was followed by panel discussions with core topics and prompt questions and panellists' responses based on their expertise, experiential knowledge based on current work, and future projections. Panels culminated with questions from and dynamic exchanges with other participants. Panel discussions were interspersed with breaks to facilitate networking and reflection. The second day also saw an engaging address on data for policy work within the public sector followed by additional panels. It closed with plenary discussions and group work to identify strategic actions to close public sector AI and data science competency gaps and foster a robust, sustainable data for policy community within West Africa.

Here are the insights from the programme in which participants examined current initiatives, identified opportunities and challenges, and emphasised the need for competence, ethics, and trustworthiness in capacity building for long-term sustainability.

4. Insights

4.1 Navigating Complexity: Data, AI, and Advanced Computation in Decision-Making

AI Integration within Government Operations

The use of digital technologies to advance governance goals is positively correlated with reduced corruption, improved governance, and increases in efficient and transparent government systems. Artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data science's analytic, predictive, and performance capabilities takes this one step further by availing unprecedented insight for decision making. They provide abundant opportunities for tackling "difficult" problems with precision and facilitating an immediate feedback loop for learning and improvement when responsibly developed and deployed.

Within West Africa, there is a broad spectrum of AI applications that go from macro to micro and cross industries and sectors. These include predictive modelling for evaluating credit ratings and assessing risk in debt-distressed countries, political risk valuations, food security risk identification and mitigation, developing resilient cash crop and tree breeds, population sentiment analysis on policy and influence, and assessment of personal gambling behaviour. Thus, the critical question has shifted from whether governments should adopt AI, to how governments can and should spearhead its integration, ensuring that it is executed with competence and a focus on the public interest.

Yet, contemporary application of AI and data science within West African governmental frameworks are highly dependent on the strengths of "traditional" institutions, political will of governing administrations, and technocratic competencies. Thus, it is of little surprise that its use greatly varies across the region – from robust systems in higher income countries (e.g., Ghana and Benin) to fledgling platforms in fragile and conflict affected states. This, coupled with the complex nature of employing AI and data science into decision-making, brings about as many challenges as opportunities.

Despite AI's uncompromising forward drive, its adoption has shown challenges. The spectre of existing biases within collected datasets looms large, threatening to further marginalise vulnerable populations in areas such as credit access and to entrench gender and racial discrimination. Similarly, algorithmic bias, where programmers' subjective perceptions skew AI learning and processing, are concerns that demand urgent attention as it has significant impact on generated insights and, subsequently, resulting decision making and investments. Equally as important are privacy concerns – from breeches that lead to unauthorised access for fraudulent purposes to fears of government misuse and abuse. Conversely, there are a myriad of opportunities made available by AI adoption. For example, Africa is and will continue to be a "young" continent with a growing number of young people seeking employment and vocational opportunities. Using data science insight for forecasting and embedding AI into academic, vocational training, professional development, and capacity building programmes can swiftly cultivate a workforce with a desired skill set (including ones ready to navigate the AI landscape).

Indeed, one should not look to the government to produce these systems but rather to enable innovation-friendly environments to springboard start-ups, business incubators, and idea accelerators, that deliver technologies meeting market and social needs and fuel a vibrant data science and AI ecosystem. Governments need to treat AI as one of many development tools to meet objectives and provide needed investment.

However, greater competency in AI and data science opportunities, applications, challenges, and management is essential to foster a welcoming environment for innovation.

There is a shared vision for governments to underscore their commitment to STEM training, framing AI as a cornerstone for development, and backing this with the necessary investment.

Additionally, for governments to leverage AI requires high-level and dedicated government-academia partnerships that focus on initiatives with aligned interests and recognise and resolve the divergence between political and research “timelines”, with the latter currently seen as “too long” for the policy landscape. For example, this can be academics and researchers co-creating “success pathways” with politicians and showing them what success looks like in the short term (i.e., in 1 year, 2 years, 3 years, etc.). Of course, industry collaboration is pivotal in bringing AI strategies and solutions from the drawing board to real-world implementation. Thus, co-creation is required for any solution addressing competency with special emphasis on learning pathways to address strategic talents and skill gaps.

The non-negotiable commitment to ethical AI use highlights the crucial need for ethical and regulatory frameworks that not only foster but also protect user rights. The trustworthiness of AI systems hinges on strengthening community bonds, ensuring that strategies for implementation are not only resonant but also inclusive. This involves engaging communities through co-creation or co-ownership. Achieving this, however, is contingent on maintaining stringent standards of security and user privacy during the adoption and implementation of AI technologies. Given the varied social and contextual realities across countries, and the inherently cross-boundary nature of digital technologies, there is an imperative for regions to adopt the most robust systems. Such an approach ensures that no one is left behind, either due to lack of access or concerns over privacy breaches.

Sustainability in AI hinges on evidence of its efficacy and practicality, i.e., its ability to affect and improve citizen’s lived experiences. Elements such as establishing data hubs to counteract silos and enhance the survey potential and evaluation of government programmes are evidence-based examples of AI strength and sustained use. Such evidence should also emphasise understanding and integration of the ethical and effective use of generative AI in public, academic, and private instructions. Sustained use should also consider AI applications in addressing pertinent and pressing regional challenges such as assessing regional stability, migration, food security, and climate change. Additionally, sustainability must promote tools and techniques that enhance data quality – especially where data collection is not coordinated and/or sparse. The Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique (SMOTE) is useful in this regard. All this can only be accomplished through a multi-stakeholder and multi-iterative approach.

4.2 Fostering a Vibrant GovTech Industry across Africa

Balancing proprietary and open principles to accelerate the government's utilisation of data analytics and AI in delivering fair and trustworthy public service

As industry plays a pivotal role in AI adoption and use, the dialogue also examined the growing GovTech arena. GovTech is characterised by the World Bank as a holistic approach to public sector reform, aimed at creating citizen-focused, accessible, and efficient digital government services. While it streamlines bureaucracy, digital transformation in GovTech may not fully address the dynamic needs of the public, especially within the growing role of ICT firms in data collection. Today, GovTech transcends mere digital modernisation, representing any technology serving the government as its main market. This synthesis of private innovation and public sector goals is poised to revolutionise how the government interacts with people and businesses, with the agility to adapt services to the swiftly evolving demands of the public.

The current scope of GovTech is expansive and dynamic. These include projects where transportation technology companies share non-sensitive operational data to aid government decision-making, such as pricing strategies.

GovTech also means readiness from the public sector to articulate, design, and co-create technologies for public service delivery.

Thus, public sector initiatives are resourcing metropolitan, municipal and district assemblies with the logistical support necessary to effectively utilise government tech infrastructure. Furthermore, foundational steps are being taken to furnish schools with ICT tools needed for scaling up AI opportunities, setting the stage for a tech-savvy future generation. However, challenges arise from inconsistent data quality, the relevance of generated data to contextual needs, and the limited internet access, which particularly affects small-scale farmers.

Collaborative models that encourage innovation and establish trust are at the heart of GovTech expansion. Conducting a needs assessment to pinpoint gaps in tech infrastructure, synergies, and areas ripe for innovations, co-developing models with the private sector, and rolling out pilot projects for realised efficacy are essential steps in this process. These pilots not only test best-fit models for broader application but also serve as crucial indicators of stakeholder engagement. Establishing trust is also an ecosystem-wide endeavour and stakeholder buy-in is a key driver of trust. Thus, there is a need for end-user representation in system development and the promotion of physical platforms for brainstorming, ensuring all voices are heard, including those from civil society organisations and start-ups, for holistic design and delivery of GovTech products. For example, scaling up technologies requires informing people about and giving them space to understand and see benefits of AI and, conversely, invest in infrastructure, capacity development, and skills training for sustainability.

Collaboration also extends to data collection, privacy, and security, which remain paramount. With the development of community data exchange models, governments can implement collaborative models for co-creating, designing, and sharing community data. Adherence to data minimisation principles is crucial, as is obtaining community consent, particularly when engaging students in participatory skill building programmes, like coding clubs, where parental consent is a requirement.

However, there is a current lag in infrastructure readiness which highlights the need for executive (political) leaders to be the driver of digital transformation. Political will is essential for accelerating technological and industry needs assessments, capacities, competencies, infrastructure, integration, and use, all elements critical to strategic decision-making and social and economic growth. Additionally, identifying and engaging stakeholders along the “data science and AI value chain” are essential for addressing innovation and idea generation, as well as fostering public-private partnerships for meeting infrastructure needs. Meeting public sector needs and achieving public benefit necessitates interconnected, coordinated, and future-oriented solutions that facilitate use. Solutions should also be workable, thus able to meet today’s objectives and agile to adapt to rapidly evolving social needs, and future-thinking. Most importantly, they should enable and drive government investment, ownership, and/or stake in GovTech systems. Consequently, this will require public sector ability to spearhead national content creation and digital skills acquisition, implement ‘right first time’ data-sharing agreements and delineate exit strategies with longer-term views on ownership and acquisition (e.g., Initial Public Offerings).

Governments must show a willingness to engage with advisory and development institutions when addressing implementation gaps regarding GovTech systems. This presents a significant opportunity for partnerships and scale-up as the role of international partners can be multifaceted. They connect expertise across various sectors and offer broader perspectives on case studies.

They also may provide technical research and knowledge exchange for stakeholders and diversify funding opportunities for the development of GovTech solutions. This potential expansion of the “resource purse”, though not essential, provides an avenue to thinking long-term and driving innovation on a larger scale.

Yet, platforms for international collaboration and knowledge exchange are most crucial for growth. This may include but not be limited to an exchange of ideas, research, and products; sharing and exchanges between government and private platforms through API systems; or, even more important, creating an enabling environment for regional and continental infrastructure sharing. Sovereignty and security considerations are integral in developing these models, with transparent, explainable systems and data-sharing agreements laying the foundation for trust. Therefore, frameworks for future collaboration should be simple, applicable, and flexible, promoting deep appreciation, ownership, and implementation. Involving young researchers can facilitate buy-in, while ensuring that these frameworks are inclusive, especially, for example in agriculture, for small-scale farmers to drive youth interest in agriculture.

4.3 GovTech and enabling country systems – Sector Focus: Agriculture

Collaborative efforts to advance country systems for risk management

The advancement of AgriTech systems is critical for responsive governance in agriculture. These systems enhance the depth and quality of data, which serves as the backbone for developing decision-support tools that inform and improve policy systems and outcomes. By promoting the exploration of cost-effective project alternatives, AgriTech supports market creation and optimisation, directly influencing value-chain activities crucial for the establishment of fair pricing structures. Moreover, AgriTech's potential in climate-proofing is noteworthy, addressing key issues such as policy incoherence and tailoring insurance design policies to the varying needs and characteristics of the agricultural sector and aid in market aggregation and mechanisation efforts. Given its outsized role, it is important to keep abreast of what is happening within the subsector, know how to strategically invest to improve outcomes, and share strategies, technologies, and learnings wherever applicable.

In implementing GovTech systems, particularly those geared toward agriculture, there are both opportunities and challenges. Whether endogenously or exogenously driven, governments now show increased willingness to collaborate with advisory bodies and international development institutions to address food insecurity. However, challenges persist with inconsistent linkages due to varying data quality and competence in generating useful data. Often, systems that generate data may not align with the situational contexts and lived realities they aim to serve. This results in data produced lacking the necessary information to effectively scale up solutions. Furthermore, binding constraints such as access to finance and infrastructure persists. For example, small-scale farmers frequently encounter limited access to internet services, which hampers their ability to benefit from technological advancements.

To effectively scale up AgriTech solutions, it is essential to prepare farmers to embrace and utilise the technologies, such as those that employ artificial intelligence. Naturally, this involves fundamental capacity development and skills training to elevate farmers' technological literacy and competency. Nonetheless, it is crucial for practitioners to recognise the expertise and deep understanding that farmers - or any trades people with whom they collaborate - possess about their work. Their knowledge about their needs and the way assistance should be provided is invaluable. Hence, a co-creative approach that respects and incorporates this expertise is vital for the development of sustainable systems. Such systems empower individuals to harness new advancements that can significantly elevate their productivity and competitive advantage in the marketplace.

As previously stated, the role of international partners in contributing to the advancement of AgriTech and GovTech in agriculture cannot be understated. Their involvement avails technical and research resources for scholars, policy makers, and practitioners. Such partnerships can unlock diverse funding opportunities and foster the connection of expertise across various fields, driving innovation and providing a more holistic understanding of agriculture and its interconnectedness to other happenings such as climate change, migration, and trade.

Moving forward, it is imperative researchers, practitioners, and policy makers work together to establish and employ frameworks for collaboration. These frameworks should be co-created to be simple, applicable, and flexible, encouraging a deeper appreciation, ownership, and implementation among all stakeholders, particularly farmers. Conducting thorough needs assessments will help streamline these frameworks, making their integration and operations effective and relevant. Additionally, considering the outsized role agriculture plays in the region and its demographics, it is important to include and involve young and early career researchers. Their points of views facilitate buy-in from and ensures that

frameworks developed are inclusive and attractive to young people, potentially sparking a renewed interest in agriculture among the younger generation. This is particularly important in small-scale farming, which is the foundation of much of the region's agricultural sector.

4.4 Impact of West-African Research at the Nexus of Data and Policy

Data for Policy's Role in Shaping West African Policy Practice

In the dynamic landscape of West African policy practice, local research occupies a pivotal position at the nexus of data and policy, directing policy with empirical evidence from both traditional and innovative sources. This research, often focused on practical and timely challenges, offers transformative insights that are shaping decision-making processes. Sub-Saharan Africa stands at a crossroads, where the burgeoning power of data science and AI meets policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation, transforming research ideas into essential tools for policy-making.

The integration of AI into data science and policy necessitates a paradigm shift from "traditional" statistical to impact-based modelling. This shift underscores the need to adopt a user-centric approach that enhances trust and utilises AI's predictive capabilities to better understand stakeholder needs and to pre-emptively identify weaknesses within policy frameworks and expenditures, thereby allowing for more robust and resilient governance. Given highlighted opportunities and challenges, AI research agendas should, ideally, be set by projects that promote collaborative need- and issue-identification and idea conceptualisation. AI outcomes, as previously noted, should enable end-users to navigate and leverage transformative processes. Such research avoids presumptuous conceptualisation, balancing the demand and supply dynamics of funders and research gaps, and is backed by evidence justifying funding and allocations. This user-centric approach results in a better appreciation of needs and improves trust. It also extends to research dissemination, where simpler approaches are needed to translate academic rigor into policy-relevant briefs. Thus, national AI policies spearheaded by leadership, along with the necessity to maintain a fine balance between AI and human intelligence to derive meaningful insights for data and policy initiatives, are necessary.

When evaluating research projects that have made their mark in West Africa, one sees that projects gain significance through their collaborative approach to issue identification and conceptualisation, setting a robust research agenda aligned with stakeholder needs. They avoid assumptions and instead promote inclusive participation and balance the oft-competing demands of funders with the pressing research gaps. Evidence-based justification for research fund allocations ensures that these projects are not only relevant but also sustainable. Of course, most research projects do not happen within a vacuum. Researchers and practitioners are aware of both the political and funding environments. Thus, it is critical to develop projects that align with funder priorities and strike a balance between the supply of research needs and the demand for actionable insights. Utilising generative tools, such as evidence gap maps, ensures that research interests align with the 4A's - Availability, Awareness, Accessibility, and Affordability - making research outcomes more appealing and practical for end-users.

In the sphere of impact measurement, the importance of reskilling and upskilling to harness the full potential of data science in policymaking cannot be understated. Building capacity through multidisciplinary research teams and aligning research agendas with governmental plans enhances the relevance and uptake of research findings. Sharing best practices and establishing platforms for partnerships facilitate knowledge exchange, which is crucial for informed policy development. To ensure collaboration, solutions must be tangible and transformative.

For data to continue to effectively influence regional policy, it should embody the principles of 'CAN' (Change, Automation, Novelty) and be transformative as indicated by the 'DIMI' (Data, Interventions with a Multiplier Impact) and 'PIMI' (Policy Interventions with a Multiplier Impact). Data's role extends beyond mere numbers to its system and the people managing it, so there should also be a focus on fostering innovation and novelty. It answers to both research needs and workforce development, ensuring that capacity is not just only built but also remains. This approach to data underscores the need for a data science roadmap to fill policy gaps and ensure that policies are not only statistically targeted but also realistic and comparable with other benchmarks.

To further strengthen West Africa's role in the global data for policy debate, there should be concerted efforts in promoting reskilling and upskilling, building multidisciplinary research teams, and aligning research agendas with government plans. Sharing best practices and creating platforms for partnerships are also critical. Solutions for growth and collaboration involve transforming lives through policy and data agendas, simplifying complex research for policy application, fostering national AI policy leadership, and maintaining a balance between AI and human intelligence for meaningful data insights.

DfP is recognised for its potential to serve as a central nexus, with its ability to offer independent perspectives and broker relationships across ministries, countries, and regions. Its reach, through platforms like the *Data and Policy* journal, can amplify the impact of West African-led research and foster deep collaboration. Regional stakeholders should leverage DfP's unique position to bridge gaps identified, thus propelling the regional data and policy interactions.

4.5 Convergence of Technology and Grassroot Engagement

Balancing emphasis on national-level digital transformation with unique contexts, needs, evidence, and tangible impacts from grassroots engagements

The convergence of technology and grassroots engagement in the context of public service delivery is a complex yet vital area for exploration, particularly in balancing national-level digital transformation with unique local needs and contexts.

Multi-faceted technology has demonstrated transformative potential in enhancing services, such as providing crucial agricultural weather briefs and early warning systems and offering tailored SMS messages to mitigate post-harvest losses. The application of AI in educational settings (e.g., in exam monitoring) reduces labour needs. Additionally, technology facilitates greater inclusion in governance, as seen in research and experience with the political inclusion of previously underrepresented voices and provides vital advisory services through online spaces on sensitive health issues (e.g., the proliferation of health apps).

Despite these advancements, the integration of technology at the grassroots level faces critical challenges. The increased cost of internet services and poor connectivity in rural settings hinder widespread adoption. This digital divide not only limits access but also affects the transfer of competence and skills necessary for effective utilisation. Moreover, there are inherent risks involved, including the potential for fraud, victimisation, grooming risks related to age, sex, and/or gender, impact on local rights, and the perpetuation of religious hate and sensitive materials (e.g., violence). Such issues further exacerbate the inequality gap, particularly affecting those already trailing in digital literacy.

Addressing these disparities requires a nuanced approach that balances the uniformity of digital initiatives with the contextual variabilities of local communities. This balance can be achieved through stakeholder engagement from the conceptualisation to the implementation stages of technology-driven initiatives. Emphasising the decentralisation of GovTech is crucial in ensuring that local needs and contexts are adequately addressed. Developing

partnerships to enhance technology use at the grassroots level and creating mechanisms to deepen trust in public policy can foster a more inclusive digital landscape. Furthermore, promoting accountability in policy design and engaging in collaborative learning can bridge stakeholder differences and facilitate incremental understanding across diverse communities. This approach not only addresses the immediate needs of local communities but also sets the stage for a more equitable and effective public service system, leveraging the full potential of technology to meet the diverse needs of society.

5. Conclusion

Strategic consultations in Nairobi and Accra have been pivotal in shaping a collective commitment to enhance cross sector collaboration and public sector competency and readiness for AI and data-driven decision making. Despite the promise of AI, challenges such as data biases and privacy concerns persist, necessitating ethical frameworks and community engagement in AI adoption. Sustainability in AI is dependent on its practical impact on citizens' lives; thus, it requires evidence of efficacy, ethical use, and multi-stakeholder approaches.

GovTech is emerging as a transformative force. Yet, governments need to balance proprietary technology with open-source principles to improve public service delivery. Collaboration models are central to accomplishing this. It is also essential to manage GovTech's expansion, prioritising innovation, trust, and the addressing of infrastructure and skill gaps. For Sub-Saharan Africa, AgriTech is particularly important as it improves data quality and informs policies for agricultural risk management and market optimisation. Given the significant role of international partners in the sector, they should be part of contributing technical resources and funding opportunities to facilitate innovation and grow a strong AgriTech and, in general, GovTech ecosystem.

To realise future aspirations and goals, stakeholders must create frameworks for collaboration that are inclusive and adaptable, and actively engage young researchers to foster generational renewal and innovation, particularly in agriculture. DfP is poised to play an invaluable role as a facilitator and connector that amplifies West African-led research and promote and technically support advocacy for a cohesive data science and AI landscape that meet the rapidly evolving needs of both the public sector and society at large.

6. Recommendations

At the closing, a plenary session was held asking participants to recommend actionable next steps based on the two days of dialogue and discussion, personal reflection, and future aspirations. Participants were also asked to consider DfP's three core axioms:

- Bridging the gap between advanced computational and technological research, ensuring research is not only understood but its insights are effectively applied in policy and practice
- Merging global platforms for collaboration and sharing research, findings, and systems with local knowledge generation, innovation, and impact
- Harmonising private sector's proprietary and frontier dynamics with open, responsible innovation aimed at public benefit

They were also informed of the delivery of that framework via a consortium model, where DfP specialises in nurturing an ecosystem that generates actionable insights from sophisticated and rigorous data analysis. The current and proposed range of programme activities includes:

- Organisation of global conferences and regional dialogues for knowledge sharing and networking.
- Publication of cutting-edge research and methodologies in the *Data & Policy* journal
- In-house and contracted research and projects along our core axes
- Leadership fellowships for capacity building in data-driven policy making, targeting researchers' data communication and visualisation skills, and analysts and policy makers' understanding of data, analysis, and application skills.
- Provision of open, online platforms to support the above activities.

Resulting recommendations underscore the importance of ensuring inclusivity, security, and the integration of AI and data science within societal and government systems to enhance open data practices and bolster data protection. They advocate for comprehensive education in data and AI, with special emphasis on local relevance and the development of GovTech ecosystems that cater to diverse linguistic communities. Capacity building is essential, with a focus on strategic partnerships and community engagement to support effective policy implementation. DfP is envisioned as a central platform to foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and to enhance global connections, while also facilitating funding opportunities and capacity building for impactful data-driven policy and investment decision making. The spirit of these directives is to create a collaborative, educated, and technologically empowered society where policy and practice are interwoven seamlessly and answer to the public good.

Component	Recommendations
High Level High Urgency Primary Issues	<p><i>Inclusivity, security, and the integration of AI and data science practices into broader societal and governmental frameworks</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting open data practices, ensuring data is accessible and freely available for use and distribution • Strengthening data security and implementing robust measures for data protection to safeguard sensitive information • Encouraging data sharing protocols that facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange while maintaining privacy standards • Enhancing effectiveness of data protection agencies to ensure they are capable and efficient in overseeing data management practices • Focusing on capacity development through targeted training programmes and resources to build expertise in data management and AI • Emphasising need for orientation and education in digital practices to raise awareness and understanding of data and AI technologies • Boosting digital literacy across all sectors to enable individuals and organisations to engage effectively with digital tools and technologies • Developing local ecosystem, particularly in GovTech, to foster a supportive environment for innovation and application of AI in governance • Advancing language translation capabilities to break down linguistic barriers and facilitate wider access and usability of digital platforms • Prioritising inclusion of diverse communities to ensure that digital initiatives are equitable and beneficial to all sectors of society • Establishing comprehensive national and regional AI policy frameworks to guide the ethical and effective use of AI technologies • Integrating AI into existing issues and systems rather than treating it as a standalone solution, to maximise its impact and relevance
What Should We Amplify	<p><i>Education, local relevance, and effective implementation in the context of data, AI, and GovTech development</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a comprehensive national strategy for data and AI, outlining clear objectives, standards, and practices to guide integration and advancement of these technologies • Prioritising education in data science and AI, ensuring that individuals across sectors are equipped with knowledge and skills to engage with these technologies effectively • Building local content by enhancing language competency, thus ensuring that digital platforms and AI tools are accessible and relevant to diverse linguistic groups • Focusing on development and application of AI for local languages, to ensure cultural relevance and to broaden the impact of technology in local communities • Establishing a GovTech lab to strengthen local networks, fostering communication and collaboration among stakeholders, including government, academia, and the private sector • Bridging gap between policy formulation and its practical implementation, ensuring that policies are effectively translated into tangible, impactful actions and initiatives

<p>What Can We Offer</p>	<p><i>Capacity building, policy alignment, strategic partnerships, and community engagement</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering expertise in the drafting and development of comprehensive strategies for data, AI, and GovTech initiatives • Focusing on capacity building to enhance skills and knowledge in relevant sectors, ensuring a strong foundation for effective implementation • Organising advocacy workshops to raise awareness, educate stakeholders, and mobilise support for technology-driven initiatives • Engaging in outdoor activities to identify key players in the tech ecosystem, fostering connections and collaborations • Emphasising the design of systems with privacy considerations at the forefront to ensure the protection of subjects and users • Implementing targeted online advertising campaigns to reach and educate users of these systems, increasing awareness and engagement • Providing facilitation support, such as field experts and 'trainer of trainers' programmes, to share knowledge and implement practical use cases • Building partnerships with the right organisations to leverage collective strengths and resources for greater impact • Offering institutional support to provide a stable foundation for the successful execution of projects and initiatives • Conducting comprehensive scans of existing policies to identify scope, gaps, and areas for recommendation, ensuring alignment with current standards and needs • Facilitating cross-learning by sharing examples and use cases, enhancing understanding and application of best practices • Providing resources for facilitation and engagement activities, enabling thorough and effective implementation of initiatives
<p>Role of DfP</p>	<p><i>Facilitator and enabler with capacity to engage, connect, inform, and support stakeholders efficiently and effectively</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving as a dynamic platform for continuous collaborations, engagements, and knowledge sharing, fostering an environment of ongoing learning and community growth • Facilitating connections at national, regional, continental, and global levels, linking key stakeholders and field experts to enhance cooperation and leverage diverse expertise • Forming and supporting regional hubs - in partnership with domestic organisation - to implement objectives • Prioritising capacity building to empower individuals and organisations, especially those within the public sector, with skills and knowledge necessary for effective data utilisation and policy-making • Collaborating and co-producing projects to access and manage resources more effectively • Assisting in the facilitation of funding opportunities and expanding networks, helping stakeholders to identify and secure necessary financial support and forge valuable partnerships

7. Annex

Strategic Consultation Agenda

25-26 October 2023 | ISSER Annex, University of Ghana, Legon

Programme Day 1

Participant Arrivals | ISSER Annex

09:30 Programme Check-in
Tea & Coffee

10:00 Welcome

Peter Quartey, PhD

Director | Institute of Statistical Social & Economic Research, University of Ghana

Zeynep Engin, PhD

Founding Director | Data for Policy CIC

Editor in Chief | Data & Policy, Cambridge University Press

Andrew Hyde (Virtual)

Publisher, Academic Journals (Data Science) | Cambridge University Press

10:20 Opening Address

Olubunmi Ajala, PhD

Special Advisor to Minister | The Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovations and Digital Economy, Nigeria

10:30 Introductions

10:45 Tea & Coffee

11:00 Navigating Complexity: Data, AI, and Advanced Computation in Decision-Making

How is AI being integrated within government operations?

- Existing AI initiatives and projects within governments in areas of agriculture, climate action, and fragility
- Opportunities and challenges in AI adoption
- Considerations of competence, ethics, and trustworthiness
- Strategies for capacity building and long-term sustainability

Peter Olugbenga Adeleye, PhD

Acting Director General | Institution of Data Scientists and Analysts

Elikplimi Komla Agbloyor, PhD

Associate Professor | University of Ghana Business School

Forster Boateng, PhD

Deputy CEO, Operations | Tree Crops Development Authority

Henry Nunoo-Mensah, PhD

Senior Lecturer, Department of Computer Engineering and Programmes Coordinator, Responsible AI Laboratory | Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology

Chair: Rislán Abdulazeez Kanya, PhD

Deputy Vice Chancellor - IT, Research, and Innovation | Baze University, Abuja

12:00 Lunch | Pagoda Area

13:00 Fostering a Vibrant GovTech Industry across Africa

How can we balance proprietary and open principles to accelerate the government's utilisation of data analytics and AI in delivering fair and trustworthy public service?

- Current scope and application of GovTech
- Private sector's ability and role in delivering GovTech vision - collaboration models that encourage innovation, build trust, and support public principles
- Data collection, privacy, and security in private-public information sharing
- Practices on infrastructure readiness, skill development, standardisation, and continuous improvement and adaptation
- Highlighting opportunities for partnership, scaling, and replication

Jemima Adjanor

Chief Technology Officer | SolarTaxi

Amon Bazongo, PhD

AI Engineer & Consultant | Intelliances

S Martial Anicet Kiemde, PhD (Virtual)

Analyste d'affaires TI | Le ministère de la Cybersécurité et du Numérique du Québec

Abena Nyamesem

Head of Sustainability and Partnership | Ghana Investment Funds for Electronic Communications

Ridwan Sorunke (Virtual)

Advisor, Founder, & Chair | Dev-Afrique

Chair: Peter Quartey, PhD

Director | Institute of Statistical Social & Economic Research, University of Ghana

14:00 Gov-tech and enabling country systems – Sector Focus: Agriculture

How can collaborative efforts advance country systems for risk management?

- AgriTech systems and their role in responsive governance (i.e., AgriTech and climate-proofing)
- Data and investment infrastructure, policy, and people readiness for GovTech (AgriTech) usage at scale
- Opportunities and challenges when implementing gov-tech systems, generally and agriculture specific
- Meeting expectations and tackling challenges by leveraging country and regional partner contributions
- Role for international partner contribution

- Frameworks for future collaboration and development

Samuel Benin, PhD

Deputy Director, African Regional Office | International Food Policy Research Institute

Temitope Odedeyi, PhD (Virtual)

Research Fellow, Optical Networks Group | University College London

Camillus Abawiera Wongnaa, PhD

Senior Lecturer, Department of Agricultural Economics, Agribusiness and Extension | Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology

Stanley Wood, PhD (Virtual)

Senior Program Officer | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

Chair: Forster Boateng, PhD

Deputy CEO, Operations | Tree Crops Development Authority

15:00 Day 1 Conclusion

15:15 Tea & Coffee

15:30 Adjourn

19:00 Dinner | African Regent Hotel, Kheepe Room, Second Floor

Programme Day 2

Participant Arrivals | ISSER Annex

09:30 Programme Check-in
Tea & Coffee

10:00 Recap / Setting the Stage
Diasmer Panna Bloe
Researcher | Data for Policy CIC

10:05 Day Opening Remarks
Samuel Kobina Annim, PhD
Professor of Economics, Government Statistician | Ghana Statistical Service

10:20 **Evaluating Impact of West African-led Research at Nexus of Data and Policy**
How has local research in data and / for policy shaped West African policy practice?

- Overview of significant research projects
- Utilisation and optimisation of data science and AI
- Impact measurement methodologies, results, and knowledge exchange
- Challenges and opportunities for further growth and collaboration
- Policy implications and future directions

David S. Ameyaw, PhD

President and CEO | International Center for Evaluation and Development

Rislan Abdulazeez Kanya, PhD

Deputy Vice Chancellor - IT, Research, and Innovation | Baze University, Abuja

Michael Kodom, PhD

Research Fellow | Institute of Statistical Social & Economic Research, University of Ghana

Racine Ly, PhD (Virtual)

Director, Data Management, Digital Products and Technology | Akademiya 20673

Chair: Diasmer Panna Bloe

Researcher | Data for Policy CIC

11:30 Tea & Coffee

12:00 **Convergence of Technology and Grassroot Engagement**

How can countries balance the emphasis on national-level digital transformation with the unique contexts, needs, evidence, and tangible impacts arising from grassroots engagements?

- Role of technology in enhancing public service delivery, especially at the grassroots level
- Discrepancy in digital transformation prioritisation and resource allocation (national ↔ local)
- Balancing uniformity and contextual variability and divergence
- Evidence of local communities experiencing positive local benefits and how to leverage for general impact
- Best practices for optimising systems for co-creation, local evidence, **and** local impact

Joshua Amo Adjei, PhD

Associate Professor | University of Cape Coast

Hamadiyah Alhassan, PhD

Associate Professor | University for Development Studies

Ahmed Dooguy Kora, PhD

Professor, Director of Training and Research | L'Ecole Supérieure Multinationale des Télécommunications

Charlie Martial Ngounou

Executive President | AfroLeadership

Chair: Roselyn Adadzewa Otoo

Project Director, Retail Finance Distribution | Institute of Statistical Social & Economic Research, University of Ghana

13:00 Lunch | Location

14:15 Group Dialogue / SMALL GROUPS

Data for Policy in SSA: Action Plan 2024-2027

Does proposed action reflect current thinking, happenings, best practices, and future aspirations?

- Translating proposed theory of change to real-world applications that promote future-oriented innovations and produce tangible benefits in the data for policy ecosystem
- Measuring up to and aligning with our exchange on vision, strengths, gaps, opportunities, challenges, and viable initiatives

Zeynep Engin, PhD

Founding Director | Data for Policy CIC

Editor in Chief | Data & Policy, Cambridge University Press

Diasmer Panna Bloe

Researcher | Data for Policy CIC

Stanley Wood, PhD (Virtual)

Senior Program Officer | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

15:15 Closing Remarks

Peter Quartey, PhD

Director | Institute of Statistical Social & Economic Research, University of Ghana

15:30 Adjourn

8. Partners' Profiles

Institute of Statistical Social and Economic Research

The Institute of Statistical Social and Economic Research (ISSER) is a semi-autonomous institute within the College of Humanities at the University of Ghana. We are recognized as one of the leading social science research institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa. Our primary focus is to conduct research, provide training, and engage in outreach and dissemination activities that promote the socio-economic development of Ghana and Africa. With a distinguished faculty of over 25 PhD-holding members and a network of local and international collaborators, ISSER is at the forefront of shaping policies and driving positive change in and beyond Ghana.

Website: www.isser.ug.edu.gh

Social: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn: ISSERUG

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

The [Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation](#), based in Seattle, USA, is one of the largest charitable foundations in the world. It works to give all people the chance of a healthy, productive life. For developing countries, the focus is on health improvement and relief from hunger and poverty, whilst in the USA it strives to improve high school and post-secondary education, and economic mobility and opportunity.

Funding is directed to innovative ideas with the potential to remove barriers, with the foundation believing that the essential role of philanthropy is to back promising solutions which are unaffordable to government and business. Grants are awarded to organisations to achieve measurable impact in the fight against poverty, disease, and inequity around the world; these account for over 90% of funds given. Strategic investments are made with entrepreneurs, companies, and other organisations to create incentives that harness the power of private enterprise to create change for those who need it most.

The foundation funds work in 144 countries, and has offices worldwide, including in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia; Abuja, Nigeria and Johannesburg, South Africa.

Cambridge University Press

Founded in 1534, Cambridge University Press ([CUP](#)) is the oldest university press in the world. Today, CUP is a global organisation, publishing academic-level research, reference and higher education textbooks across a wide range of disciplines. Its online repository Cambridge Core hosts 1.6 million journal articles and 46,000 e-books, granting academics access to high-quality, digitally interconnected materials that enhance understanding and the global impact of research. CUP currently publishes more than 380 peer-reviewed academic journals, as well as thousands of books for research and education. CUP has offices and publishing hubs in more than 40 countries, with CUP Africa based in Cape Town, South Africa.

Evans School of Policy Analysis & Research Group, Evans School of Public Policy & Governance, University of Washington

The Evans School Policy Analysis & Research Group ([EPAR](#)) at the University of Washington's Daniel J. Evans School of Public Policy & Governance provides rigorous, applied research and analysis to international development stakeholders.

Thematically, EPAR focusses on inclusive agricultural transformation, development policy, financial services, poverty reduction, gender, and measurement and evaluation. Most of our work is centred on countries within sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, and much of our time is devoted to increasing the utility of data from these geographies. From the World Bank LSMS-ISA household surveys we are growing a publicly available searchable database of over 100 common agricultural statistics for Nigeria and Ethiopia ([AgQuery](#)) and a [GitHub](#) repository of code that also includes Tanzania, Malawi, and Uganda. We plan to add climate data, more countries, and an adaptation focus as we launch the University of Washington's new Center on Risk and Inclusion in Food Systems.

Participating Organisations

A4AI-Ghana Consumer Advocacy and Equal Access Working Group / GIFEC
AfroLeadership, Cameroon
Akademiya 20673
BAZE University, Abuja, Nigeria
Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, USA
Cambridge University Press, UK
Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa, Nigeria
Data for Policy CIC, UK
Dev-Afrique, Nigeria
Ghana Statistical Service
Institute of Statistical Social & Economic Research, University of Ghana
Institute of Statistical, Social and Economic Research, University of Ghana
Institution of Data Scientists and Analysts, Nigeria
Intelliances, Burjina Faso
International Center for Evaluation and Development, Ghana
International Food Policy Research Institute
Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana
L'Ecole Supérieure Multinationale des Télécommunications, Senegal
Le ministère de la Cybersécurité et du Numérique, Quebec
Ministry of Communications, Innovation and Digital Economy, Nigeria
Policy Vault Africa, Nigeria
Responsible AI Network – Africa, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana
SolarTaxi, Ghana
Tree Crops Development Authority, Ghana
UCL, UK
University for Development Studies, Ghana
University of Cape Coast, Ghana
University of Ghana Business School
University of Washington

Thank You

Contact Information

 africa@dataforpolicy.org

 www.dataforpolicy.org